

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF ENERGY GENERATION DEVICE FOR SUSPENSION SYSTEM OF TWO WHEELERS

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Abstract

This project focuses on designing a device capable of generating electricity from the shock absorbers of a vehicle. The setup utilizes a rack and pinion mechanism coupled with dynamo motors, secured in place using aluminum angle bars. When a vehicle encounters a bump or uneven surface, the shock absorbers compress and extend. This movement is transferred to the rack, which moves downward and engages with the pinion gear connected to the motor shaft. As the pinion rotates, the dynamo generates electricity, which can be measured using a multimeter. This process repeats with every shock event, allowing for continuous energy production. The generated electricity can be utilized to power various vehicle components, including headlights, taillights, horns, indicators, window operations, or even to charge the battery.

Keywords: Suspension system, Dynamo, Rack and pinion.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past several decades, there has been a significant rise in the number of vehicles on the road, accompanied by a growing demand for clean and sustainable energy. This has led researchers to closely examine how energy is dissipated across various components of a vehicle. Among these, the suspension system plays a critical role. Typically, the suspension setup includes elements like tires, springs, linkages, shock absorbers, struts, and other components, depending on the design of the vehicle. Shock absorbers, in particular, are essential for dampening the impacts experienced while driving. They help absorb the kinetic energy produced by road irregularities, transforming it most commonly into heat, which is then released through the fluid inside the absorber. In essence, shock absorbers act as dampers, minimizing sudden jolts and maintaining ride comfort. However, the linear motion produced during the functioning of these components often goes unutilized. The concept of harnessing and conserving energy became prominent in the 20th century, sparking interest in improving energy efficiency within the automotive sector. As a result, innovations in regenerative technology have led to the development of energy-recovering suspension systems. Unlike conventional passive systems that only absorb vibrations, these advanced systems are capable of capturing mechanical energy and converting it into electrical energy. This regenerative mechanism works by transforming vertical vibrational energy generated as the vehicle moves into electromagnetic energy using systems like rack and pinion arrangements. The electricity

generated can then be stored using energy storage devices. This dual functionality not only helps in damping vibrations but also contributes to energy recovery. Following over four decades of research, regenerative suspension systems have begun to appear in both hybrid and fully electric vehicles. These systems have proven effective in boosting overall fuel efficiency and have opened up new possibilities for sustainable vehicle design. A great deal of research continues to focus on optimizing the energy recovery capabilities of vehicle suspension systems, aiming to enhance their integration in next-generation transportation solutions. analysis, thermography, and acoustic emission, work to identify problems early and take prompt corrective action. The comprehensive analysis of roller bearing failures under various operating conditions such as load, speed, temperature, lubrication state, and environmental factors is the main goal of this paper. It addresses more recent issues like contamination and misalignment in addition to more conventional ones like wear and fatigue. The study also highlights the significance that contemporary diagnostic techniques like vibration analysis, infrared thermography, and acoustic emission play in early failure identification. The potential of advanced predictive maintenance solutions, especially those that integrate machine learning and artificial intelligence, to transform condition monitoring and failure prevention in industrial settings is also examined.

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2. OBJECTIVE

1. To study existing solutions and theoretical papers available on the internet.
2. To fabricate a model which can directly produces energy from shock absorber damps or bumps.
3. To build budget friendly or low-cost model that will be solve the existing current problems as standard as possible.
4. To fabricate electricity generator device from shock absorber damps from locally available materials.
5. To experiments and analyzing our proposed model on different road conditions and performance evaluation.
6. To evaluate the performance of our fabricated device with actual trails on vehicle shock absorbers.
7. To fabricate a device using our proposed idea which will recover waste energy during frictional movement of shock absorber system and convert it into electricity

3. METHODOLOGY

1. Study of existing solutions given by authors in theoretical papers available.
2. Study of various methods used for waste energy recovery system from suspension system.
3. Experimentally determine the energy generating capacity of our model and comparing it with actual energy generated.
4. Manufacture energy generator from shock absorber suspension system.
5. By setting up our system in two-wheeler front fork shock absorbers will carry out actual readings for various road conditions & then compare the results of both Theoretical and actual readings with our device. The broader significance of this study lies in enhancing the recovery of waste energy in during damping in suspension system.
6. Our system will consist of four Brushed Dc 12v motors connected in series with pinion mounted on motor shaft moving over fixed rack when the displacement in shock absorber is achieved on road bumps while riding the vehicle. All the components of the project will be mounted on angle bars with nut and bolt.

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the paper titled " A Review on Energy-Regenerative Suspension Systems for Vehicles", the authors Zhongjie Li, Lei Zuo*, JianKuang, and George Luhrs, WCE 2013, July 3 5, 2013, Ravindra Bhoite, Somanath Jadhav, Akshay Jape, Vikram Phadatare, Amardip Jadhav "Energy Generation by Suspension System 2015" In this project they have developed a suspension energy generation unit by using rack and pinion method. It is less costly than the hydraulic unit. Here, when the suspension

works, the rack is set moving in a reciprocating motion. Due to this, the pinion starts rotating. The rotation of the pinion is then amplified into rotation of a higher rpm by using the gear box. At the end of gear box we have attached the generator which generates the electricity.[7] R. B. Goldner and P. Zerigian with J. R. Hull, in "A Preliminary Study of Energy Recovery in Vehicles by Using Regenerative Magnetic Shock Absorbers "SAE Internationals 2001 set up a periodic road bump simulator test stand, This was in the form of a grinder that had one of its grinding wheels replaced by an aluminum disk which had a rounded, adjustable height, "bump". Which is a schematic of the test stand with a (non-optimized) model magnetic shock absorber is a permanent magnet to produce electricity.[8]

Chirangivee.K. R in "Design and Fabrication of Power Generating Shock Absorber" 2016 this device consists of two components in the form of piston and cylinder arrangement a hollow cylinder with surface coil assembly and a magnet assembly that uses vibrational energy from the vehicle's suspension to move up and down inside it to generate the electricity using shock bumps. [9]

Kashif Wani, "SUSPENSION BASED KINETIC ENERGY RECOVERY SYSTEM" November December 2016 made circuit that works by picking up the signals from the suspension movement and convert it into electricity.[10] Himanshu S. Rewatkar, Vicky R. Gedekar, Kunal L. Parate, "Power Generation by Using Suspension System",2017 In this project authors have to develop a suspension energy generation unit by using belt and pulley Here, the pulleys are mounted on the shaft of the DC motors. As the pulleys get rotated the shaft of the motors also get rotated which generate electricity. [11] Suhail A. Wani, "Kinetic Energy Recovery System for Vehicle Suspension", 2020.The authors regenerative shock absorber converts this kinetic energy into electricity instead of heat through the use of a Linear Motion Electromagnetic System. Shock absorbers are installed between chassis and wheels to suppress the vibration, mainly induced by road roughness, to compensate for bumpy roads and provide riding comfort. [12] authors emphasized that persistent wear causes surface pitting and scuffing, which in turn causes catastrophic failure, especially in contaminated conditions [2].

Furthermore, Shi and Yang (2022) investigated the This paper deal with mechanical motion rectifier which convert the oscillatory vibration into unidirectional rotation of the generator.[5] In the paper titled " Power Generating Shock Absorber ", the authors Meghraj P.Arekar , Swapnil Shahade Volume 4, Special Issue 3, March 2015: Designed The Power-Generating Shock Absorber (PGSA) converts this kinetic energy into electricity instead of heat through the use of a Linear Motion Electromagnetic System (LMES). [4] In the paper titled "Design of Electromagnetic Shock Absorbers for Energy Harvesting from Vehicle Suspensions", the authors Pei Sheng Zhang 2010: This paper discussed about the different type of suspension system. Also, the rack and pinion arrangement in vehicle suspension. [13] Rahul UttamraoPatil, Dr. S. S. Gawade, "Design and static magnetic analysis of electromagnetic regenerative shock absorber" This paper discusses electronic equipment

systems are precision system. There are some vibrations and impact in moving.

Working

When the sudden shocks or potholes or uneven surface comes in contact with the tyre it gives bumps and tends to move the front fork shock absorbers inward and hence motion in linear direction is achieved. The device is connected to the front fork shock absorber so that when the vehicle is over a bump it will move the racks on the down side and the pinions are mounted on the shaft of the motor and meshed with the racks the motor will generate electric and the springs attached to the motor frames are also pushed in opposite direction causing it to contract and the energy stored in the spring will take the mechanism back to its original position voltage which can be measured with multimeter. And the process continues and power production cycle will repeat this produces energy can be used to illuminate the headlights, taillight, horn, indicators or charge the vehicle battery.

Design And Calculations

Power calculations

1. The use of 12V motor is being done in the project (4) quantity in series connection to charge 12V battery for voltage required in series connection
2. $V_s = v_1 + v_2 + v_3 + v_4 = 12 + 12 + 12 + 12$
 $V_s = 48V$ But in actual practice the V_s is the voltage required to run 4 motors in series.
3. The rpm of motor is 10000rpm and maximum operating ampere is 10amp/hr. So, Unit watt consumption $V \times I \times t = 12 \times 10 = 120 \text{ watt/hr}$
4. The battery in the automobile is commonly vary from 12V 5amp to 12V 25amp in case of four-wheeler the capacity of battery for 2-wheeler is
 $(V \times 1) \text{Capacity}$
 $= 12 \times 5 \text{ (Assuming 5amp battery)}$
 $= 60 \text{ watt/hr}$
5. Assuming that the four series motor system generates 2V in one actuation & 0.1amp Capacity = $2V \times 0.1 \text{ amp} = 0.2 \text{ watt per actuation}$ on road bump.
6. Assuming case of power generation capacity if shock absorber come across 40-30 shocks or bumps the power generation would be actual during Breaking, Acceleration, Speed breaker and sudden shocks. Probably vehicle would come across 80-100 bumps so power generation would be $P_{gb} = 0.2 \times 80 = 16 \text{ watt}$ will be generated.
7. So, time required to charge the 2-wheeler battery would be $B_g = 120/16$ $P_{gb} = 7.5 \text{ hrs}$ So the system almost takes 7.5 hrs or 1600 bumps or shock to charge the battery to full capacity.

Testing And Results

The actual project consists of four 12V motors connected in series with rack and pinion mechanism which tends to move linearly when subjected to shock or bumps the

mechanism is connected to bike with shackle. The rack is attached to the movable part of the shock absorber which tends to move and pinions are stationary in position hence meshing and movement of rack and pinion mechanism.

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Table 1 Testing and Results

Sr. No.	Pitch movement of shock absorber in cm	Power generated in volts	Load on vehicle in Kg
1	2	0.12-0.20V	80
2	4	0.25-0.30V	80
3	6	0.45-0.50V	80
4	8	0.54-0.69V	80
5	10	0.72-0.92	80
6	12	0.92-1.08V	80
7	Full length	1.2-1.5V	80

5. RESULTS

1. During testing it has been observed that the average power generation rate is 0.5V per shock or bump.
2. The rate of power generation depends upon the pitch moment of shock absorber and no of shocks or bumps come across vehicle.
3. The rate of power generation depends upon the depth of bumps or shock pods it has been observed that the higher will be the depth of shocks or bumps faster the power generation.
4. The maximum voltage generated is 1.5V on the total length of the rack and pinion and 0.1-0.2V on the minimum move of the shock absorber.

6. CONCLUSION

We conclude our project, from the testing results it has been observed that the average power generation from the bump or shock is 0.5V for heavier shocks it generates voltage ranges from 1.2V to 1.5V the testing has been carried out on the road bump or road shock pitch depths independent of load applied and vehicle suspension energy.

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